

SOUTHERN OCEAN OBSERVING SYSTEM

Report Series

SOOS Datathon Incheon, South Korea May 15, 2019

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SOOS Datathon

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Report on activities

The SOOS Datathon (Incheon, South Korea, May 2019) was a collaboration between the SOOS Scientific Steering Committee and Data Management Subcommittee, held in association with the SOOS annual meetings. The aim of the datathon was to get scientists and data managers working together to solve data challenges facing the Southern Ocean research community and that

The aim of the datathon was to explore data challenges facing the Southern Ocean science community; to solve small data

challenges; to scope out larger data projects; and to make progress on a number of ongoing SOOS data projects. Potential projects were scoped in advance of the meeting by canvassing members of the SOOS Scientific Steering Committee and Data Management Sub-Committee for ideas on which small groups could make significant progress in a single day of focussed effort.

This is an interim report on the day's activities, highlighting areas of future activity for the project groups.

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Group 1: Reviving historical physical and chemical oceanography data

Irene Schloss, Petra ten Hoopen, Steve Diggs and Pip Bricher

Several sets of historical long-term physical and biological datasets from the Antarctic Peninsula were identified as potential targets for digitisation and reanalysis in conjunction with modern observations. Discussions focussed on a series of full-depth physical observations (temperature, depth, salinity, chemistry) taken from under sea-ice at Brown Station and Melchior Station on the Antarctic Peninsula that was acquired by Gustavo Ferreyra and colleagues in the 1960-80s and that are in the process

of being digitised. SeaView was used to identify spatially collocated observations that may be suitable for temporal comparisons. During discussions, gaps were also identified in the publication of RaTS data (Rothera Oceanographic and Biological Time Series).

Future activity: Irene Schloss and Gustavo Ferreyra to investigate opportunities for studentships and suitable candidates to perform the comparisons and, as a by product, prepare and document the historic data for publication. Petra ten Hoopen to discuss the gaps with the RaTS data creators.

Group 2: Oceanographic mooring metadata

Joana Beja, Povl Abrahamsen, Melissa Zweng, Yuhua Pei, and Mike Williams

The SOOS Mooring Network is an index of approximately 800 oceanographic moorings that have been deployed in waters south of 40S since 1944 and can be [found through SOOSmap](#). The data from these moorings is housed in data centres around the world and, in some cases, the location of the data is still unknown. The SOOS science and data communities have gathered basic metadata about these mooring deployments, including links to the data repositories, where available. This index thus acts as a central discovery tool for moorings and may, in the future, identify targets for best-practice standardisation of formats, metadata, and observational units.

At the datathon, this group of data managers and oceanographers worked through the SOOS mooring network list to identify errors and omissions in the list.

Future activity: Where metadata details about a mooring, including data publication information, could not be readily identified, group members assigned individuals to contact data owners. Using the Amundsen Sea as a test case, the group will ask data owners to convert their data to a consistent format. Additionally, the group plans to identify potential mooring synthesis projects that use the data (e.g. shelf waves, tides, or other features that might be interesting at regional or circumpolar scales; perhaps a reference for seal-borne data loggers; ecosystems/biochem) that could act as a catalyst for further data standardisation and integration work.

Group 3: Biogeochemistry data aggregation

Sian Henley, Jo Beja, Rob Sherrell, Patricia Yager, and Sarah Fawcett

Biogeochemical data are highly variable in terms of data format, parameters, and data management practices. There are several aggregations of biogeochemistry data available to Southern Ocean scientists but none of them are comprehensive, either in terms of parameters or datasets. This group envisions SOOSmap providing a central discovery point for all key biogeochemical data holdings, even if it is not serving up the data itself. Discussions on the scope of activities needed to achieve this vision suggested that this would take a number of

years and likely requires dedicated human resources to undertake them.

For the carbonate system, the group identified SOCAT as a core data aggregation and with to add in more variables, while minimising the duplication of effort.

Future activity: The group will email community members to identify gaps in the data aggregations discussed in this session. Members will also look at data layers of nutrient concentration at various depths and identify tasks for students and interns that will make progress towards an eventual vision of all Southern Ocean biogeochemical data being discoverable through SOOSmap.

Group 4: BEPSII chlorophyll data from fast-ice cores

Klaus Meiners, Benedicte Pasquer, and Marco Alba

On behalf of the SCAR [Biogeochemical Exchange Processes at the Sea-Ice Interfaces Expert Group](#) (BEPSII), Klaus Meiners has aggregated chlorophyll data from ~800 cores taken from fast ice near Antarctic research stations. [The data](#) are in standardised .xlsx files and published through the Australian Antarctic Data Centre. For publication in SOOSmap, these data need to be converted

to a netCDF format. This group explored several data files, and Benedicte Pasquer agreed to undertake the data translation on behalf of Australia's Integrated Marine Observing System (IMOS).

Future activity: Benedicte Pasquer (IMOS) will standardise and clean the 800 files for publication. SOOS IPO and the EMODnet Physics team will coordinate its publication through SOOSmap.

Group 5: Southern Ocean glider data needs

Sebastiaan Swart and Bastien Queste

There are three key data assembly centres for glider data - [Everyone's Gliding Observatories](#) (EGO), the [US Integrated Ocean Observing System](#) (IOOS), and [Australia's Integrated Marine Observing System](#) (IMOS), which are negotiating paths to standardise their data formats for better integration in the future. However, not all Southern Ocean glider data

have been submitted to one of these DACs and the Southern Ocean glider community has not yet agreed on a coherent set of data needs. This group drafted a [summary report](#) on SOOS' glider needs and recommendations for data centres and scientists who work with gliders to standardise their data formats and data handling procedures, so as to improve the interoperability of glider data in years to come. This report asks scientists working

with gliders to follow international standards and states that SOOS will use its Regional Working Groups to encourage submissions to the DACs and to the [World Meteorological Organisation's Global Telecommunication System](#) to improve data interoperability and reuse.

Future activity: SOOS Regional Working Groups will be asked to encourage all glider-using scientists in their regions to submit all relevant data to one of the key glider DACs or to another trusted repository, in a standardised format.

Group 6: BODC-SeaDataNet-EMODnet Connections

Jo Beja and Marco Alba

[EMODnet Physics](#) developed and hosts [SOOSmap](#) for SOOS as a central portal to discover key standardised and well-curated datasets for the Southern Ocean, in addition to serving European marine observation data. [SeaDataNet](#) is a source of aggregated data for EMODnet, drawing from European data centres, including the [British Oceanographic Data Centre](#). It appears that only ~2500 of ~10,000 SOOS-relevant datasets from

BODC are being served through SOOSmap. This group traced the data flows to identify the reasons why not all relevant BODC datasets are flowing through to SOOSmap and identified activities needed to rectify the flows.

Future activity: This group will follow up with colleagues at BODC, SeaDataNet, and EMODnet to ensure that the identified errors are corrected.

Group 7: CTD data flows

Taco de Bruin, Marco Alba, and Steve Diggs

SOOSmap, as an aggregator of data from multiple data pathways, faces increasing issues of duplicated datasets, where individual observations have been aggregated in multiple locations without always great traceability. Using CTDs as an example, this group mapped potential duplications and gaps in the feeds that go to

EMODnet and SOOSmap. This activity will act as a template for exploring the data flow-paths for other data types into SOOSmap.

Future activity: This group will identify sources of CTD data that aren't yet in EMODnet and identify sources of CTD data that should be excluded to minimise duplication.

Conclusion

The 2019 SOOS Datathon provided an opportunity for SOOS scientists and data managers to undertake focussed work to identify areas of potential collaboration. The day's projects ranged from narrowly scoped hands-on metadata checking, in the case of the mooring network group, to scoping long-term needs and the shape of broad data management efforts that will require funding and resourcing, in the case of the biogeochemical data group. Ongoing tasks have been identified for scientists, SOOS working groups, technical data managers, and those who manage data flows among data systems. These activities target a range of scientific challenges of particular interest to the SOOS community, including biology in the fast ice zone, carbonate chemistry, and physical oceanography.

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SOOS is an initiative of the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research and the Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research

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